

OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the large-scale reforms being carried out in our country to improve the pedagogical skills of specialists, the issues of improving the professional training of future biology teachers in higher education institutions. It also presents scientific research on achieving the effectiveness of professional activity, professional orientation, opinions on the issues of organizing professional activity based on innovative approaches and applying the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications in practice to improve the educational process.

Keywords: professional training, improving professional training, professional competence, professional activity, professional orientation, biology education, professional adaptation, innovative, pedagogical technologies, educational effectiveness.

The fourth priority area of the Development Strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, entitled "Fair social policy, development of human capital", sets the task of creating the opportunity for every citizen to study in a specific profession at state expense, increasing the scope of vocational training by 2 times, and training a total of 1 million unemployed citizens in professions. Based on these tasks, it can be said that the issue of using the most advanced educational technologies in the training of future professionals in higher educational institutions and training comprehensively mature, highly skilled specialists who can meet international standards is urgent.

Also, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system", adopted on

November 6, 2020, set out the main directions for further development of the education and science sectors in Uzbekistan in the new period of development in order to improve the education and science sectors of our country, further increase respect for teachers and pedagogical staff, scientific and creative intellectuals in our society, develop the professional skills of teachers, and expand the participation of the private sector in the system.

Speaking about improving the professional training of future specialists, let's first dwell on the concept of profession and its essence. The concept of profession is an occupation that requires special training, constantly experiences a person and serves as a source of livelihood for him. A profession unites people engaged in the same activity, and certain ties and moral norms are established within this activity.

E.A. Klimov emphasizes in his research work that "A profession is a necessary and valuable sphere for society, requiring physical and mental strength from a person." V.G. Makushin notes that a profession is an activity that, with the help of which, a person participates in the life of society and serves as the main source of material means for his livelihood. "So, a profession is the main form of labor activity, and to perform it, a person must have certain knowledge, qualifications and skills, special abilities and developed important professional qualities."

For any professional, one of the conditions for achieving the effectiveness of their professional activities is, first of all, the professional readiness of the specialist. According to the famous Russian psychologist I.K. Platonov, "professional preparation is a subjective state of a person who considers himself capable and prepared to perform the necessary professional activity and strives to perform it.

According to E. Seytkhalilov, B. Rakhimov and N. Azizkhodzhatova, "professional preparation is the process of mastering theoretical knowledge, skills and qualifications that allow a person to engage in a specific type of professional activity." R. Ishmuhamedov, A. Abdukodyrov and A. Pardayev emphasize that the basis of professional preparation should reflect "the psychological, psychophysiological, physical and scientific theoretical and practical preparation of

the future specialist”. In this regard, the concept of professional competence is also of particular importance. Professional competence is the deep development of the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of professional activity by a future teacher learning and applying them in practice.

The need to develop the professional training of future biology teachers in higher education institutions is manifested in the following:

- the use of international experience in the field of biology education and achieving educational efficiency;
- improvement of modern, innovative technologies in the education system;
- the growth of societal needs and demand for quality education;
- the transformation of the modern teacher in society;
- optimization of DTS and curricula.
- improvement of biology teaching methodologies;
- creation and implementation of new generations of electronic information educational resources in biology;
- the role and importance of the most advanced educational technologies in the methodology of teaching biology is increasing day by day
- the development of a sense of self-awareness in future biology teachers, the development of a system of value relations regarding the environment and existence, etc.

Thus, the development of professional training of future biology teachers is the process of forming special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as spiritual and moral qualities in a person based on the requirements of the State Educational Standard, the physiological, psychological and physical preparation of a future specialist for the successful conduct of professional activities.

In the literature on pedagogical and vocational education, the concept of “vocational orientation” is emphasized as having the following meanings:

- 1) “Vocational orientation” is a person’s ability, interests, need and firm belief in a specific type of activity (A.B. Seyteshev);

2) “Vocational orientation” is the dominance of the relationship between the choice of profession, interest, firm belief and motives for choosing a profession in personal qualities (N.K. Stepankova). In the works of some researchers, attempts are made to reveal the essence of the concept of “orientation to the pedagogical profession”, taking into account the orientation of a person directly to a specific professional activity.

In particular:

1) “Orientation to the pedagogical profession” - a person’s “interest in the pedagogical profession and desire to engage in this type of activity” (N.V. Kuzminova);

2) “Orientation to the pedagogical profession” - attitude towards learners, enthusiasm for pedagogical work, pedagogical observation skills.

Pedagogical scientist V.A. Slastenin emphasizes the need to take into account the following when forming the professional skills and qualifications of future teachers:

1) specific situations in which a specialist must work;

2) his work tasks;

3) the required knowledge, qualifications and skills.

Based on the professional needs of future biology teachers, it is important to systematically and consistently implement the following tasks for their professional development: - striving for self-development; – striving to acquire life and professional experience; – having a high level of preparation and motivation for teaching; – applying the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications in practice to organize professional activities based on an innovative approach and improve the teaching process.

Professional qualities are one of the important factors of success in pedagogical activity, they are characterized by such aspects as goal-orientedness, determination, ability to divide attention, diligence, observation, pedagogical tact and development of pedagogical imagination, social activity, initiative, setting a personal example,

and direct contribution to the further enrichment of universal and national values. This, in turn, creates the need to solve the following tasks related to increasing the effectiveness of the process of professional adaptation of future biology teachers:

- to determine the content of professional adaptation of future biology teachers based on the modern demands and proposals of the labor market for the training of pedagogical specialists; - to identify pedagogical and psychological factors and conditions that form the innovative potential for the qualitative acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and qualifications; - to determine and implement in practice the pedagogical conditions of professional adaptation based on a systematic approach and an environment of creative cooperation; - to develop and implement in practice new publications, electronic textbooks, educational and methodological complexes that serve the socio-pedagogical aspects of professional adaptation of future biology teachers, theoretical issues and independent education of students.

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